

Integrated Crop-Livestock and Climate Outcomes: Literature Review and Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart
Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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Report Overview

The coupling of crop and livestock production systems can provide a wide range of agronomic, economic, environmental, and land use productivity benefits (Delandmeter et al., 2024). While integrated crop and livestock (ICL) systems were historically prevalent across the United States, over the last century ICL systems have disappeared from the landscape with agricultural specialization in both cropland and livestock systems (Smart et al., 2021). However, over the past two decades there has been a revival in interest and implementation of ICL systems as a way to meet multiple sustainability goals and enhance economic diversification. A specific interest in ICL systems' potential contributions to mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and improving soil carbon storage has emerged as a burgeoning research area across diverse production contexts (Franzluebbbers & Hendrickson, 2024). This report aims to synthesize the growing body of literature on integrated crop-livestock (ICL) grazing of cash crop and non-cash crop residues in annual croplands to assess its potential benefits and tradeoffs for greenhouse gas emission reductions, soil carbon storage, and other agroecological services.

Historical and Current Prevalence of ICL Systems

Over the past century (1925-present) integrated crop and livestock agriculture has disappeared from agricultural regions across the US - with the steepest declines in grazed cropland occurring in the Northern and Central Plains (72-80% decline) (Smart et al., 2021). Similar trends of decline in total number of farms and diversity of crops grown are documented across the US (Meehan et al., 2011; USDA, 2025). While many forces may be at play in driving this steep decline, the decoupling of cropland and livestock agriculture correlates with increased agricultural specialization and industrialization. This specialization was promoted through a suite of dynamic actions such as governmental policies, easily accessible fossil fuels, increased promotion and use of synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, technological advances in machinery, storage, and distribution, as well as the rise of global markets (Hilimire, 2011; Russelle et al., 2007; Sulc & Franzluebbbers, 2014).

In recent years ICL systems have re-emerged in the US as a growing body of research and on-the-ground implementation suggests this management strategy may help recouple nutrient cycling, reduce reliance on petrochemical-based practices, enhance the carbon storage potential of cropland, and improve overall soil health (Delandmeter et al., 2024; Moojen et al., 2024; Smart et al., 2021). Moreover, popular approaches to soil health, agroecology, regenerative agriculture, and other sustainability movements often emphasize animal integration as a core component of their design and management systems (Noble Research Institute). Recent research has taken place across diverse regions of the US including the Northeast, Great Plains, Arid West, and Southeast - often on operational farms (Mike Loizzo, 2024; Russelle et al., 2007; Ryschawy et al., 2021; Sulc & Franzluebbbers, 2014). However, widespread adoption remains limited due to the knowledge-intensive nature of ICL systems, practical agronomic challenges faced by single-enterprise farming operations with limited logistical flexibility, and insufficient institutional support for managing transitions (Moojen et al., 2024; Russelle et al., 2007; Sulc & Franzluebbbers, 2014). Identifying strategies that improve knowledge exchange, between both farmers and researchers and among farmers themselves, as well as expand institutional support, may help to enhance adoption of this promising management system.

Agronomic and Ecological Functions of ICL Systems

Animal grazing has a significant impact on biogeochemical cycles and ecological processes in the soil that drive the processing of soil organic carbon and emission of soil GHGs (Brewer & Gaudin, 2020; Martin et al., 2016). For example, animal grazing may facilitate more direct pathways for soil organic carbon accrual, through the conversion of recalcitrant, plant-structural carbon within crop stands and residues into labile, bioavailable carbon via deposition of dung and urine. This relatively labile carbon is considered more readily available and accessible, and more efficiently utilized during processing by microbial communities (Brewer et al., 2023). As such, a larger proportion of animal-derived carbon is likely to persist as stable organic matter in the soil, compared to the more recalcitrant, structural compounds from plant-derived sources. (Liang, 2020). Crop biomass removal through grazing also triggers shifts in forage productivity and root turnover belowground, which can impact carbon deposition into the soil ecosystem (Dawson et al., 2000). Studies show that an increased productivity shift with targeted grazing can compensate for carbon removal through animal gains (Dawson et al., 2000). Although soil GHG processes under ICL management are less well understood, changes in agroecological conditions – such as the deposition of more labile and soluble nutrient inputs and the decoupling of plant residue carbon (C) from nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) through animal metabolism – can increase carbon and nutrient bioavailability. These shifts may, in turn, influence the microbial processes that drive soil GHG emission rates. The effects of animal integration on the biogeochemical and ecological processes that influence soil carbon and GHG outcomes will be considered throughout this report in the context of the literature review findings.

In addition to potential soil carbon storage and GHG shifts, there are a wide range of agronomic and agroecological impacts for croplands that may result from reintegration of animal grazing (Lemaire et al., 2014; Martin et al., 2016). As previously mentioned, the conversion of crop stands and residues through animal grazing creates more bioavailable forms of critical plant nutrients such as N and P (Brewer & Gaudin, 2020).

This addition of bioavailable nutrients in the form of urine and manure could in turn facilitate reduced reliance on external fertilizers (Jiao et al., 2024). Integrating animals can also reduce the need for mechanized equipment and chemical inputs to manage or terminate cover crop vegetation, including both intentionally planted agronomic mixtures and resident vegetation grown between cash crop cycles (Ryschawy et al., 2021). From a forage perspective, ICL systems can provide an opportunity to supplement animal forage budgets and enhance rest periods on adjacent grazing lands (Kumar et al., 2019). There may also be tradeoffs associated with ICL systems like surface soil compaction and overgrazing, which may happen if soil conditions and grazing management style are unideal (Fernández et al., 2015; Tracy & Zhang, 2008). Better understanding the nuanced impacts of climate, soil type, grazing management style, and other co-management considerations (e.g. tillage, fertility and pest management, etc.) will help to more accurately predict potential agronomic and agroecological outcomes for ICL systems across the US.

Key Questions and Considerations for GHG and Soil Carbon Impacts

The overarching goal of this report was to better understand the potential impact of cropland grazing on soil carbon storage, greenhouse gas emissions, and other agroecological services provided by ICL systems. Given the prevalence of annual cropping systems and increasing adoption of cover crops across the U.S., an emphasis was placed on considering cover crop residue management relative to other common residue management strategies including mechanical incorporation, mowing, agrichemical control, and crimping. The following questions were used to guide the literature review method to evaluate ICL systems and impacts:

- What are the potential soil GHG emission impacts of ICL systems?
- What are the potential soil carbon storage impacts of ICL systems?
- How do ICL systems contribute to the displacement of GHG emissions from mechanization?
- How do climate and soil type impact these potential outcomes of ICL systems?
- What system design, grazing practices, and co-management considerations are most effective in cropland grazing systems?
- What are the current GHG and soil carbon research gaps and opportunities for ICL systems?

Methods

A literature review process was used to identify primary research (e.g. one site, multi-site studies) that could be utilized to explore ICL management's impact on soil carbon and GHG emissions in annual cropping systems. Multiple academic search platforms were used to collect relevant research articles such as Scopus, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate. The search process combined system terms (e.g. Integrated crop livestock) with research metrics (e.g. soil carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas emissions). This results in the following list of common search terms that were used for this literature review:

System search terms:

- Integrated crop livestock (ICL)
- Crop livestock
- Cropland grazing
- Cover crop grazing

Research metric search terms:

- Soil carbon
- Soil organic carbon (SOC)
- Soil organic matter
- Greenhouse gases (GHG)

- Forage grazing
- N₂O, CH₄, CO₂

Articles were initially selected from the search platforms if the title, abstract, and keywords were relevant to the management system considerations and research objectives of this literature review. The studies were then reviewed and added to a research database if they contained relevant data that could be extracted for the review process of this report. Any studies that did not meet the management system and data criteria were noted with an exclusion reasoning and then removed from the database.

For the purpose of this report, the data extracted from relevant studies included any of the following: soil bulk density, soil organic matter, percent soil organic carbon, total soil organic carbon, total nitrogen, soil N₂O emissions, soil CO₂ emissions, soil CH₄ emissions, life-cycle CO₂ equivalent, and/or total carbon budgets. For the soil carbon metrics, the data extracted was taken from the end of the study periods while the greenhouse gas measurements were either seasonal or annual cumulative totals.

A comprehensive database was generated to collect study design considerations, climatic and soil property characteristics, control and treatment system management, and extractable data with units. For this report, the treatment system included animal grazing while the control system had just cropland. Once the data was extracted and organized into the database, CO₂-equivalent (CO₂-e) conversions were calculated for both soil carbon and GHG measurements to compare the standardized impact of ICL on control cropland treatments. The findings were then summarized by years under ICL management, climate zone, and soil type.

After performing this literature review, the total quantity of empirical studies was low, with 33 sites (from 23 studies) reporting soil carbon data and 14 sites (from 10 studies) reporting soil GHG data. Few of the studies reported all three GHG sources (CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) and soil carbon simultaneously - which resulted in uncertainty overall regarding the impact of annual cropland grazing on the net CO₂-e budget. Management covariate data was also collected to enable appropriate attribution of changes in GHG sources (Table 1). Finally, many studies were excluded due to the conflation of management effects through inadequate controls or multiple overlapping management practices. For example, many studies incorporated varied fertilizer application and tillage regimes or no non-ICL control (e.g. for grazing intensity variables), making it difficult to isolate individual effects.

Table 1: Co-management data for integrated crop-livestock studies

Category	Data Element	Description / Notes
Site Information	Climate Type	e.g., Mediterranean, Temperate, Arid
	Region	Geographic location (state, country, etc.)
	Production System	e.g., agronomic grain cropping, vegetable cropping, etc.
	Soil Texture	Soil classification (e.g., sandy loam)
	Soil Organic Carbon	Baseline soil carbon levels

	Precipitation	Mean annual precipitation
	Temperature	Mean annual temperature
Baseline Management System	Control Treatment	Description of non-grazed or conventional system
	Nitrogen Inputs	Average N fertilization rates
	Tillage Type	e.g., No-till, Strip-till, Conventional
	Irrigation Type	e.g., Flood, Drip, None
	Irrigation Frequency	Number of irrigation events per season
	Cover Crop Species	Species or mixture used as cover crop
	Cover Crop Termination	Method of termination (chemical, mechanical)
Grazing Management	Foraged Species	Grazed vegetation (e.g., cereal rye, specific cover crop mixtures, etc.)
	Grazing Style	e.g., Rotational, Continuous, Strip Grazing
	Stocking Density	Number of animals per hectare
	Grazing Duration	Length of grazing period
	Animal Species	e.g., Cattle, Sheep, Mixed
	Grazing Season	Season(s) when grazing occurred
	Residual Biomass	Biomass remaining post-grazing

ICL Activities under Consideration for Potential Climate Benefits

This literature review identified a general ICL model for annual cropland grazing that served as a basis for evaluating its impacts on soil carbon storage and greenhouse gas emissions. The system most researched was characterized by pasture-phases integrated into larger rotations of cash crops like soybean and corn and, occasionally, less common grain crops. These pasture phases ranged from a winter cover crop-style length of 4-6 months to a longer multi-season rotation period between 1-3

years. Most studies evaluated ICL systems with pasture species with individual species or species mixes of oat, cereal rye, wheat, alfalfa, cash crop stover, and other legumes. The systems evaluated in this report are complementary to the following CPSs, which may be combined to guide the implementation and best management practices for cropland grazing to achieve GHG reductions and/or soil carbon sequestration.

PRESCRIBED GRAZING (NRCS-CPS 528)

Prescribed grazing is defined as managing vegetation with grazing and browsing animals to achieve specific ecological, economic, and management objectives. Often, applications for prescribed grazing projects include a Grazing Management Plan prepared by a professional Certified Rangeland Manager. This may not be applicable on croplands of certain U.S. regions, especially those which are managed in quick cycles by contract grazing operations.

Prescribed grazing accounts for managing livestock numbers and grazing periods to adjust the intensity, frequency, timing, duration, and distribution of grazing and browsing to meet the planned objectives for plant communities, the animals, and the associated resources of a cropland field. This includes adjusting animal numbers, grazing periods, and movements based on the rate of plant growth, available forage, livestock forage demand, or other desired objectives (e.g., degree of forage utilization, targeted plant height or standing biomass, residual forage mass, or animal performance).

This practice is proposed to accomplish one or more of the following purposes:

- Improve or maintain desirable species composition, structure, productivity, and/or vigor of plant communities
- Improve or maintain the quantity, quality, and/or balance of forages to meet the nutritional needs and ensure the health and performance of grazing and browsing animals
- Reduce or eliminate the transportation of sediment, nutrients, pathogens, or chemicals to surface and/or groundwater
- Improve or maintain upland hydrology, riparian dynamics, or watershed function to reduce surface or groundwater depletion and improve naturally available moisture
- Improve or maintain soil health components and indicators, such as soil organic matter, soil aggregate stability, soil organism habitat, or increase infiltration and water holding capacity, reduce runoff and compaction
- Prevent or reduce sheet, rill, classic gully, ephemeral gully, bank, and wind erosion
- Improve or maintain terrestrial habitat for wildlife and invertebrates and/or aquatic habitat for fish and other organisms
- Manage biomass accumulation for the desired fuel load to reduce wildfire risk or to facilitate prescribed burning

- Reduce plant pest pressure from invasive and/or undesirable plants and other pests as part of an integrated plan

Grazing best management practices (BMPs) will vary, sometimes substantially, depending on regional and site-specific contexts. Generally, BMPs are considered to include high-density, short-duration [rotational grazing](#) management (Carvalho et al., 2010b). This rotational grazing strategy incorporates small paddocks that are grazed with high animal density and rotated frequently amongst larger sections of the overall landscape. This strategy facilitates longer rest periods and increased competition amongst grazing ruminants (Teague et al., 2008). This has been found to lower the duration of grazing per unit of land area and reduce grazing selectivity and the spatial heterogeneity of grazing pressure (Teague and Dowhower, 2003). Grazing should also aim to retain adequate residual dry matter based on recommendations from Certified Rangeland Managers and/or in coordination with knowledgeable grazing practitioners, which is variable depending on ecological, climatic, and management variables such as precipitation and temperature regime, soil type, topography, and management objectives.

For the purposes of this exercise, prescribed grazing is also being evaluated for its potential to reduce GHG emissions, both direct from soils as well as indirect from whole life-cycle considerations of cropland grazing (e.g. from fertilizers, pesticides, and/or relative to other residues management practices such as mechanization GHG emissions from mowing, crimping, etc.).

COVER CROPS (NRCS-CPS 340)

Cover cropping is defined as grasses, legumes, and other forbs planted for seasonal vegetation cover. This exercise is specifically evaluating cover crops that are established as part of a cropping system between cash crop cycles in rotation. This is a complementary practice, which should be considered intrinsic to the design of all grazing-based ICL systems.

Considerations for cover cropping include selecting species, seedbed preparation, seeding rate, seeding date, seeding depths, fertility requirements, planting methods, and/or termination and residue management methods that will not adversely affect crop yield, are applicable with local cartier and soil/site conditions, and are suitable for being managed via grazing and/or browsing animals (e.g. balancing palatability and protein content).

This practice is applied to support one or more of the following purposes:

- Reduce sheet, rill, and wind erosion
- Maintain or increase soil organic matter
- Improve soil aggregate stability
- Improve habitat for soil organisms
- Reduce water quality degradation by utilizing excess soil nutrients
- Reduce weed and plant pest pressure

- Improve moisture management
- Reduce soil compaction
- Supply nitrogen to the subsequent crop
- Improve habitat for pollinators, beneficial organisms, or natural enemies of crop pests

For the purposes of this exercise, cover cropping is being evaluated specifically for the purpose of integration with cropland grazing with respect to the potential of these paired practices to balance trade-offs associated with GHG mitigation and soil carbon sequestration relative to other cover crop residues management strategies.

ANNUAL FORAGES IN GRAZING SYSTEMS (NRCS-CPS 810)

This practice is defined as establishing adapted and compatible species, varieties, or cultivars of annual forage species suitable for pasture or fodder. This practice may be applied to annual cropland where annual forages are planted as part of the grazing system forage budget. This practice does not apply to the establishment of annually planted and harvested grain, fiber, vegetable, or oilseed crops. This practice does not apply to forestland or grazed forestland.

The purpose of this practice relevant to cropland grazing is to guide the selection of cover crop species and their cultivars based upon:

- Site, weather, and soil conditions present at establishment.
- Animal nutritional requirements with no or limited anti-quality issues.
- Intended use, level of management, realistic yield estimates, maturity stage, season of use, and compatibility with other species.
- Resistance to herbicide carryover and disease/insects common to the site or location

This practice is proposed to accomplish one or more of the following purposes:

- Provide or increase forage supply during periods of low forage production or to extend the grazing season for livestock
- Provide or increase regional forage supply to promote rest periods on adjacent grazing lands (e.g. rangelands, irrigated pasture, etc.)
- Reduce excess nutrients from cropland soil
- Improve soil microbial life and soil aggregate stability in cropland soils

For the purposes of this exercise, annual forages are being evaluated as part of cover cropping and specifically for the purpose of integration with prescribed grazing, with respect to the potential of these

stacked practices to balance trade-offs associated with GHG mitigation and soil carbon sequestration relative to other cover crop residue management strategies.

Does ICL Mitigate Soil GHG Emissions in Annual Croplands?

Overall, well-managed grazing on annual croplands appears to support GHG mitigation, primarily by enhancing soil carbon sequestration (+1.82 Mg ± 0.47 CO₂-e/ha/year; Table 2). However, it may also lead to a slight increase in soil GHG emissions (+0.08 Mg ± 0.07 CO₂-e/ha/year; Table 2). Overall, the annual CO₂-e budget indicates a net GHG mitigation benefit in both short-term (<5 years) and long-term (>10 years) crop-livestock integrated systems. The short-term annual Δ SOC stock accumulates relatively quickly (+2.50 Mg ± 0.90 CO₂-e/ha/year; Table 3), but the accrual rate slows over the long term (+0.87 Mg ± 0.42 CO₂-e/ha/year).

Table 2: Soil carbon sequestration from soils with grazed vs. ungrazed cover crops by years under ICL

Years under ICL	# of Sites	SOC (Mg C/ha)		SOC		CO ₂ -e	
		Control	ICL	Δ (%)	Δ (Mg C/ha/year)	Δ Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year	SE (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)
Short-term (<5 years)	10	24.57	26.12	5.0%	0.68	2.50	0.90
Medium-term (5-10 years)	12	25.76	26.95	3.9%	0.52	1.90	1.03
Long-term (>10 years)	14	41.5	43.88	11.1%	0.24	0.87	0.42
Total	36	29.37	30.90	5.7%	0.46	1.82	0.47

* Total SOC and CO₂-e values are means across all sites. Positive numbers indicate net positive sequestration under grazed relative to ungrazed croplands. SE = standard error

Table 3: GHG emissions from cropland soils with grazed vs. ungrazed cover crops by years under ICL

Climate	# of Sites	N ₂ O		CO ₂		CH ₄		CO ₂ -e		
		Δ (%)	Δ (kg GHG/ha/year)	Δ (%)	Δ (kg GHG/ha/year)	Δ (%)	Δ (kg GHG/ha/year)	Δ (% total)	Δ (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)	SE (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)
Short-term (<5 years)	6	18.2%	0.70	0.14	48.00	4.2%	0.14	9.9%	0.19	0.14
Medium-term (5-10 years)	4	23.1%	0.33	-26.2%	-49.85	5.5%	1.83	24.6%	0.10	0.10
Long-term (>10 years)	4	-11.1%	-0.13	-	-	17.3%	0.14	-11.0%	-0.03	0.05
Total	14	2.0%	0.36	-16.0%	-25.39	6.8%	0.56	5.4%	0.08	0.07

* Total SOC and CO₂-e values are means across all sites. Numbers in red indicate net positive emissions under grazed relative to ungrazed croplands. SE = standard error.

Data availability and resulting findings varied widely across climate types (Tables 4 and 5). The highest representation of studies was in humid subtropical climates, which demonstrated considerable GHG mitigation potential (11 sites; net sequestration of 1.76 Mg CO₂-e/ha/year). Although other systems were less represented, warm semi-arid climates also benefited from cropland grazing (6 sites; net sequestration of 2.11 Mg CO₂-e/ha/year). However, the direction and magnitude of impacts in other climates are uncertain. Overall, warmer climates exhibited greater GHG mitigation potential compared to colder climates. This effect also appears to depend on sufficient precipitation during the cover crop growth period.

Table 4: Soil carbon sequestration from soils with grazed vs. ungrazed cover crops by climate type

Climate	# of Sites	SOC (Mg C/ha)		SOC		CO ₂ -e	
		Control	ICL	Δ (%)	Δ (Mg C/ha/year)	Δ (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)	SE (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)
Warm Semi-Arid	6	32.64	35.45	12.6%	0.57	2.11	0.19
Semi-Arid Continental	2	57.80	56.95	-1.8%	-0.15	-0.53	0.03
Temperate	1	32.23	37.30	13.2%	1.69	6.20	-
Humid Continental	3	7.56	8.44	10.8%	0.21	0.77	0.04
Humid Subtropical	11	29.86	31.29	3.1%	0.54	1.99	0.30

* numbers in red indicate net negative sequestration under grazed relative to ungrazed croplands. SE = standard error

Table 5: GHG emissions from cropland soils with grazed vs. ungrazed cover crops by climate type

Climate	# of Sites	N ₂ O		CO ₂		CH ₄		CO ₂ -e		
		Δ (%)	Δ (kg GHG/ha/year)	Δ (%)	Δ (kg GHG/ha/year)	Δ (%)	Δ (kg GHG/ha/year)	Δ (% total)	Δ (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)	SE (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)
Semi-Arid Continental	5	-31.5%	0.04	-26.2%	-49.85	-5.3%	1.73	5.8%	0.02	0.03
Humid Continental	3	9.1%	0.04	-	-	-13.0%	-0.52	-7.5%	-0.004	0.06
Humid Subtropical	6	17.1%	0.78	14.4%	48.00	28.4%	0.28	17.9%	0.23	0.15

* numbers in red indicate net positive emissions under grazed relative to ungrazed croplands. SE = standard error

Empirical studies for soil organic carbon covered a relatively even distribution of soil texture categories (Table 6). Overall, performance ranked as follows: clayey soils (11 sites; +2.73 Mg CO₂-e/ha/year) > silty soils (8 sites; +0.99 Mg CO₂-e/ha/year) > sandy soils (4 sites; +0.81 Mg CO₂-e/ha/year). Empirical studies for soil GHG were predominantly conducted on clayey soils, making it difficult to draw generalizable conclusions for soil texture.

Table 6: Soil carbon sequestration from soils with grazed vs. ungrazed cover crops by soil type

Soil Type	# of Sites	SOC (Mg C/ha)		SOC		CO ₂ -e	
		Control	ICL	Δ (%)	Δ (Mg C/ha/year)	Δ Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year	SE (Mg CO ₂ -e/ha/year)
Clay	8	33.56	35.19	4.7%	0.74	2.70	1.11
Clay loam	3	15.27	19.54	20.4%	0.78	2.86	0.99
Silty clay loam	3	20.42	22.11	6.3%	0.70	2.58	1.93
Silt loam	5	42.19	42.52	5.8%	0.14	0.51	0.41
Sandy clay loam	2	17	22.6	23.8%	0.38	1.39	1.36
Sandy loam	2	7.85	7.97	1.49%	0.06	0.23	2.21

Considerations for Direct Animal GHG Emissions in Integrated Crop-Livestock Systems

Methane mitigation in grazing-based ruminant systems remains challenging due to high variability in emissions across feeds, animals, and conditions (Pacheco et al., 2014). Direct enteric methane (CH₄) emissions from grazing ruminants are shaped primarily by feed intake and diet, as the composition and digestibility of forages directly influence rumen fermentation dynamics and the microbial populations responsible for methanogenesis. As demonstrated in recent meta-analyses (Herliatika et al., 2024; Galyean et al., 2024), methane yield, or methane emissions per unit of feed intake, declines with higher starch and lower fiber diets. This effect is seen readily in concentrate-based diets when compared to forage-based diets, but this principle can be capitalized on with regards to incorporating grazed cover crops or post-harvest crop residue.

Gere et al. (2024) reported that beef steers grazing a diverse cover crop mix (vetch + ryegrass + radish) produced 29% less daily methane (119.1 vs. 167.1 g/day) and 36% less methane as a percentage of gross energy intake (4.3% vs. 6.7%) than those grazing alfalfa–fescue pasture, with no significant difference in intake or growth. Similarly, Maxin et al. (2020) found that several cover crop species (including phacelia, sainfoin, buckwheat, and berseem clover) reduced methane *in vitro* by 26%, 14%, 12%, and 13%, respectively, when compared to alfalfa, likely due to the presence of secondary plant metabolites such as tannins and phenolics that inhibit methanogenic archaea. Forage brassicas like rape and swedes achieved methane yield reductions of 23% and 25%, respectively, compared to ryegrass, while providing 25% greater digestibility and up to 50% more metabolizable energy (Sun et al., 2012). The inclusion of functional forbs and legumes in pasture mixes, such as chicory, plantain, and white clover, has been associated with improved nitrogen use efficiency and reduced methane emissions, though results may depend on grazing intensity and botanical composition (Wilson et al., 2020).

Beyond species selection, broader system-level strategies such as integrated crop–livestock–forestry or silvopastoral systems offer structural and ecological benefits that can further mitigate GHG emissions.

These systems have been shown to reduce daily methane emissions per hectare (Da Silveira Pontes et al., 2018) and limit manure-associated nitrous oxide and methane losses when paired with optimized diets (Rivera et al., 2021). Supplementation strategy that is associated with grazing cover crops or crop residue can also contribute to reduced direct emissions compared to perennial grazing. Supplementing stocker calves grazing winter wheat with an energy-based feed containing monensin reduced methane emission intensity, or methane emissions per unit of average daily gain, and improved growth performance, though with diminishing returns (Thompson et al., 2019). Overall, species selection and supplementation management have the potential to reduce direct GHG emissions from grazing ruminants when compared to perennial grazing systems, but there is considerable research needed to establish consistent recommendations and the magnitude of reduction for each strategy.

Life Cycle Assessment Considerations for ICL Systems

The intensification and specialization of modern industrial agriculture are closely tied to the increased use of synthetic inputs, fossil energy, and, often, irrigation. In most commercial-scale operations, crops and livestock are produced in isolation, with little to no integration. In contrast, integrated crop-livestock (ICL) systems offer a more synergistic approach to food production, with the potential to enhance environmental sustainability, economic viability, and farmer livelihoods.

ICL systems come with a wide range of environmental, economic, and social expectations. However, conducting a comprehensive or life cycle assessment (LCA) of these systems remains challenging due to the complexity of interactions between ecological and social factors at regional and systems levels. One key obstacle lies in the uncertainty and variability surrounding the definition and treatment of system boundaries. ICL systems involve the spatiotemporal integration of three interacting components—crops, grasslands, and livestock—often requiring coordination among multiple farm operations. When effectively managed, these systems can enhance soil fertility, control erosion, and improve biological regulation at the field and territorial levels (Martin et al., 2016; Moraine, Duru, & Therond, 2016).

Several successful cases of ICL adoption demonstrate these potential benefits:

- **High profitability and reduced environmental impacts** have been achieved in ICL systems compared to both intensive monoculture cropping systems and extensive low-productivity beef systems (dos Reis et al., 2021).
- **Replacing soybeans with faba beans (*Vicia faba* L.)** in crop rotations for fodder has improved both efficiency and appeal as livestock feed, while also highlighting the importance of soil management and reducing livestock density per unit area to maintain sustainability (Guarnaccia et al., 2024).
- **Citrus-alfalfa intercropping with swine (CAIS)** has demonstrated a lower carbon footprint per kilocalorie produced compared to other crop-livestock combinations, emphasizing the importance of waste exchange, optimized manure treatment, and system-level planning to mitigate GHG emissions (Zheng, Liu, & Pan, 2023).

- **Seasonal sheep integration in vineyards** has shown ecological and economic advantages over conventional viticulture, offering a model for sustainable diversification (Niles, Garrett, & Walsh, 2017).

To realize the full potential of ICL systems, state and federal policy incentives should support the development of strong social networks, facilitate shared understanding of integration benefits, and reduce long-term monitoring and transaction costs (Schut, 2021; Ryschawy et al., 2021). Operational costs, for instance, can be offset by scaling integration across larger areas and engaging more participants (Asai et al., 2018).

How does Integrated Crop-Livestock Grazing Fit within a Broader Residue Management Regime?

Adoption of ICL grazing may be best understood not as a fixed or stand-alone residue management practice, but as one potential component within a flexible, adaptive residue management strategy designed to meet evolving agronomic, ecological, and operational goals. Rather than prescribing a single approach, successful ICL systems often integrate grazing alongside other management strategies such as mowing, roller-crimping, and even occasional tillage, as part of a broader multi-year rotational residue management framework.

Each residue management strategy offers distinct trade-offs, and their appropriateness can vary by season, weather conditions, crop type, livestock needs, soil health status, equipment access, and overarching farm objectives. Mowing or mechanical shredding, for instance, may be preferable in wet field conditions when trampling and compaction risks from livestock are high, or when grazing logistics (e.g., fencing, water access) cannot be easily managed. Similarly, roller-crimping may serve as an effective method for uniform cover crop termination, particularly in organic systems where herbicides are avoided, and where uniformity of mulch cover is desired for weed suppression or moisture retention.

Grazing, by contrast, introduces biological interactions that not only reduce surface biomass but also cycle nutrients through animal metabolism, enhancing nutrient availability and potentially stimulating belowground carbon inputs via root regrowth and exudates. Grazing can be especially advantageous when crop and/or cover crop biomass is abundant or excessively fibrous, as ruminants help convert low-quality residue into labile organic matter inputs through manure and urine deposition. Strategic grazing can also displace the need for mowing or tillage, reducing fossil fuel use and labor costs while generating co-benefits like animal weight gain, weed suppression, and improved rest periods on adjacent grazing-based lands.

However, grazing is not always the optimal or feasible choice. During wet seasons or in poorly drained soils, the risk of compaction may outweigh the benefits. Likewise, if grazing intensity is poorly timed or unmanaged, it can reduce ground cover excessively, increase erosion risk, or compromise nutrient cycling. As such, adaptive management that accounts for site-specific constraints and system goals is essential. For instance, a producer might rely on roller-crimping in early spring to terminate a cover crop

ahead of a cash crop planting, use grazing in fall to manage regrowth and reduce residue bulk, and selectively incorporate tillage every few years to manage compaction or reseed perennials.

Ultimately, ICL grazing may be most effective when applied as part of a systems-based, adaptive residue management regime that complements other practices rather than replacing them completely. Through this strategic layering of tools, farmers may better manage residue biomass, enhance soil function, reduce synthetic input reliance, and balance productivity with long-term ecological health.

Research Needs

The overall number of empirical studies remains limited, with only 33 sites (from 23 studies) reporting soil carbon data and 14 sites (from 10 studies) reporting soil greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. There is a clear need for more integrated crop-livestock (ICL) research across a broader range of climates, soil types, and co-management regimes. Notably, few studies measured all three major GHGs (CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) alongside soil carbon, limiting our ability to assess the net CO₂-equivalent (CO₂-e) impact of grazing on annual croplands. Future studies should prioritize measuring emissions and sequestration processes concurrently to improve overall system assessments.

A significant number of studies were excluded due to confounding management variables, such as overlapping fertilizer applications, tillage practices, or seeding techniques, and a lack of appropriate controls (e.g., fallow treatments). These issues hinder the attribution of observed effects to cropland grazing alone. This speaks to the myriad of research needs for practitioners of ICL, as existing research attempts to meet multiple objectives beyond questions pursued in this report.

Addressing these research gaps is essential for field-scale GHG quantification and verification, particularly in support of process-based biogeochemical models. These models require extensive empirical data with wide spatial and temporal coverage for accurate calibration and validation. Long-term research trials are extremely underrepresented within ICL research. Because grazing substantially influences nitrogen cycling, ICL systems would benefit from coupled carbon-nitrogen models like DNDC or DayCent, which can better capture feedbacks to improve estimation accuracy.

Current ICL research also falls short of supporting assessments at regional or system-wide scales. Future research should prioritize the studies on the tradeoffs and scalability of the establishment of long-term ICL experiments, surveys in key regions, a portal for citizen science, and more engagement with ICL system farmers (Garrett et al., 2017). Broader boundaries, including adjacent land-use impacts and whole-system dynamics, remain underexplored. While LCAs have been applied in some ICL contexts, they often vary in their treatment of system boundaries. Nonetheless, LCAs represent a promising approach for quantifying both total and per-acre indirect emissions linked to cropland grazing adoption and should be more widely implemented in future research.

Summary

Integrated crop-livestock (ICL) systems may offer a diverse array of agroecological functions that can contribute meaningfully to climate change mitigation while enhancing agricultural productivity and resilience. In the 21st century, interest in animal grazing within cropping systems has grown, as

emerging research highlights the potential of ICL systems to meet evolving agricultural and environmental objectives. This literature review finds that well-managed grazing can support greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation, whether through cover cropping or pasture rotations on annual cropland. Although soil-based GHG emissions may increase slightly under ICL systems, this is offset by gains in soil carbon sequestration driven by animal grazing, resulting in a net climate benefit. Evidence also suggests that ICL system outcomes vary by climate zone, with warmer regions potentially offering greater GHG mitigation potential. However, limited data from colder or more arid climates underscores the need for further research in these regions. Similarly, soil type influences ICL outcomes, with clay-rich soils showing the most substantial improvements in soil organic carbon under grazing. Additionally, species selection and supplementation management have the potential to reduce direct GHG emissions from grazing ruminants in cropland when compared to other grazing systems, particularly due to control over cover crop species selection. Overall, ICL systems show promise as GHG mitigation strategies, particularly when tailored to specific climatic and edaphic conditions. Further research is essential to clarify the complex interactions between climate, soil characteristics, and management practices, and to refine grazing strategies that maximize the climate benefits of integrating livestock into cropland.

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